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Incorporating a Motion Analysis Research Laboratory into a Dynamics Course using Model Eliciting Activities

B.P. Self¹

Professor, Department of Mechanical Engineering
California Polytechnic State University
San Luis Obispo, California USA
E-mail: bself@calpoly.edu

D.J. Montoya and K. Mavrommati
Students

California Polytechnic State University
San Luis Obispo, California USA
E-mail: djmontoy@calpoly.edu and katherine.mavrommati@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Undergraduate dynamics is often one of the most challenging courses in an engineering curriculum. Creating meaningful assignments that provide engineering context is challenging, and problems often seem contrived and lack authenticity. To help motivate students, we try to bridge the gap between typical homework assignments and tasks that they may encounter in their engineering careers. One way to achieve this is through the use of Model-Eliciting Activities (MEAs). The Rowing MEA introduced students to the study of human biomechanics and allowed them to record motion data of a rower in the Cal Poly Human Motion Biomechanics Lab. In the MEA, a fictional gym equipment manufacturer wanted to improve the design of their latest rowing machine. In a post-activity survey, 83% of students agreed or strongly agreed that the Rowing MEA was more interesting and engaging than other in-class activities, 90% agreed or strongly agreed that they learned skills that would aid them in future real world applications of dynamics, and 77% agreed or strongly agreed that the MEA presented a realistic scenario that an engineer might encounter at their job.

Conference Key Areas: Engineering Education, Attractiveness of Engineering Education, Engineering Education Research

Keywords: Model-eliciting activities, dynamics, inductive learning

¹ Corresponding Author
B.P. Self
bself@calpoly.edu

1 BACKGROUND

1.1 Model-eliciting activities

The ability to assimilate different information and create usable models is a critical skill for engineers. Equally important is the ability to frame and solve ill-defined problems. A fairly new technique in engineering which evolved in the mathematics educational community attempts to address these skills by creating problem sets called Model Eliciting Activities (MEAs)[1]. Teams of students are provided with a client-driven problem, most commonly in the form of a request from a fictitious company. These problems are open-ended and force the students to fuse information in a way that is not typically encountered in homework problems. The process of working in a team-based environment, developing a systems-based approach to solving the problem, plus developing and refining conceptual models are all important skills that can be learned in an MEA (in addition to its technical content). Developing higher-order thinking and strong problem solving strategies are as (or more) important to a working engineer as their technical knowledge.

The MEA has several salient differences from other problem-based exercises [4]. Traditional exercises typically involve selecting the correct equations, applying a “cookbook” approach, and coming up with a correct answer. Laboratory exercises and creative hands-on exercises in engineering classrooms often have a similar approach. MEAs require students to develop a conceptual and/or mathematical model, then refine it by comparing it to the customer needs. This design, test, revise cycle is the crux of many undergraduate design courses. These MEAs can begin the process of developing strong open-ended problem solvers before students are required to complete a year-long capstone design project.

Diefes-Dux et al. [2] discuss a useful framework to use when developing an MEA. There are six basic principles that should be used [2,3].

Model Construction Principle: The MEA should require students to develop a process, description, and/or a mathematical model to address the needs of the client. This is not constrained to simply a mathematical equation – it may take the form of a set of procedures, an algorithm, a set of instructions, or graphical models. There should also not be one correct answer – students should struggle with the open-ended nature of the MEA. It can also be beneficial if a certain degree of discovery learning takes place in the process.

Reality Principle: A true engineering-based, client-driven problem should be motivational and realistic for the student. Placing lecture and textbook knowledge in an industrial or research context will help students realize how their skills may be used in the future.

Self-Assessment Principle: The MEA should include sufficient criteria for the student to test and possibly change their conceptual/mathematical models. This often comes in the form of sample data, or as in our Rowing MEA, students actually collect data to help them validate their models. Team members should be able to assimilate their previous knowledge to make some judgment on the quality of their solutions.

Model Documentation Principle: A deliverable product documenting student thinking should be produced at the end of the MEA. This is typically in the form of a memo to the company, but could also be in the form of a computer program, algorithm, or even a physical product. Their documentation helps students to review and reflect upon the development of their model, and allows the instructor to examine

the students' conceptual understanding of the material and their problem solving strategies.

Generalizability Principle: A strong MEA requires the solution to be readily adaptable to similar problems or situations. In our Rowing MEA, students were asked to adapt their model to test the effects of different seat heights. Creating generalizable models is often difficult for the students, who tend to create very specific solutions for the exact problem they are given.

Effective Prototype: Student teams should be able to produce a solution that is “as simple as possible yet still mathematically significant.”[2] The teams should be asked to revisit the model repeatedly as they progress, making sure that their models employ sound engineering principles. The MEA should also involve concepts that will be important in their future engineering classes and careers.

1.2 Context of study

The students were enrolled in an intermediate undergraduate dynamics course that also contains a significant Matlab programming component. The class meets for three 50-minute lectures and a 2-hour computer laboratory each week. The Rowing MEA was assigned in the middle of the 10-week quarter, and consisted of two different computer laboratory sessions. Approximately 30 minutes of the first session was used to familiarize students with the Human Motion Biomechanics Laboratory (<http://hmlab.calpoly.edu/>) and to collect data. During the second laboratory session, students worked on the assignment, primarily developing Matlab code to determine the kinematics of the athlete when using the rowing machine.

1.3 Human Motion Biomechanics Lab

The exerciser using the rowing machine was analysed in the Human Motion Biomechanics Laboratory (HMBL) at Cal Poly. The HMBL uses a series of 10 cameras, capturing in synchronized time at 150 frames per second, to collect motion data. Near infrared LED clusters surrounding each camera's aperture emit high intensity light at the capture volume within the lab. Retroreflective markers affixed to the subject and equipment in the capture volume then reflect this light directly back towards the aperture of the cameras. The video processing software Cortex, from Motion Analysis (Santa Rosa, CA), is used to collect and process data from the cameras in real time. Cortex locates the centroid of each marker's reflection, then calculates and displays the X, Y, and Z location of the marker for each frame of the video. Once the capture is completed, Cortex is used to post process data. Post processing includes naming markers, interpolating data where markers were obscured, smoothing data, and exporting in .csv format.

1.4 Rowing MEA

The memo provided to the students for the Rowing MEA is provided in the Appendix. As indicated previously, the memo is from a fictitious company that would like the students to (1) predict the hip marker location after a marker has fallen off using rigid body kinematics and to (2) investigate the effects of altering the seat height on leg kinematics. A picture of a subject rowing with kinematic markers is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Subject using the rowing machine with kinematic markers on various anatomical landmarks.

The six principles of MEAs and how they are met in the Rowing MEA are provided in Table 1.

Table 1. How the Rowing MEA meets the MEA principles.

Principles	How the Rowing MEA Meets the Principle
Reality	A fictitious fitness company requests kinematic analysis of their product, and also asks about changing their design
Model Construction	Students develop a linkage model of the lower leg and a computer program to analyse the motion
Generalizability	The students create a model that allows them to change the seat height as well as the linkage lengths. This could be applied to any crank-slider mechanism.
Effective Prototype	Students can check their kinematics starting from the ankle to the knee, then progress to check the hip velocity. Rigid body kinematics are utilized in many engineering applications
Self-Assessment	Students are given position data for the first 2 or 3 seconds before the marker falls off, so they can check data against their kinematic calculations
Model Documentation	Students create a computer model, including an animation to help visualization of the motion. Additionally, they write a memo back to the client communicating their efforts.

The Rowing MEA fits under our classification of a Physical Model-Eliciting Activity, or P-MEA, where an actual experiment is used to either collect data and/or for utilization in self-assessment [5].

1.5 Research goals

Our goals were to (1) determine if the Rowing MEA increased student interest and motivation, (2) examine how well the assignment fulfilled the principles of an MEA,

(3) explore areas for improvement in future implantations of MEAs involving the Human Motion Biomechanics Lab.

2 METHODS

2.1 Subjective Survey

A subjective survey was administered to the students. Out of the 119 students who completed the assignment, 52 completed the survey. Students rated the following statements listed in Table 2 on a Likert scale: Strongly Agree, Agree, Neutral, Disagree, Strongly Disagree.

Table 2. Survey Questions rated according to Strongly Agree, Agree, Neutral, Disagree, or Strongly Disagree

Question Number	Survey Question
1	The rowing lab presented a realistic scenario that an engineer might encounter at their job
2	The required deliverables were possible to accomplish in the time allotted
3	There are useful real world applications for the skills gained through the ME 326 rowing lab. (Matlab data processing, animations, etc.)
4	Compared to other labs, the ME 326 rowing lab was more interesting and engaging
5	This lab got me interested in applications of engineering related to biomechanics.
6	This lab got me interested in research
7	The rowing lab should be repeated in future sections of ME 326

In addition, students were asked two open-ended questions: (a) Do you have any suggestions on how to improve the rowing lab? (b) Any additional comments?

2.2 Student submissions

Additionally, student submissions were analysed to determine how closely they met the requests put forth in the client memo.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Survey Questions

Results from the survey are shown in Figure 2. Seventy-seven percent of the responding students agreed or strongly agreed that the lab presented a realistic scenario; 90% thought it involved useful real world skills. Eighty-three percent of students thought the Rowing MEA was more interesting than other labs in the course, and 87% recommended that the lab be offered in future sections of the class.

An additional interest of ours is to see if introducing students to the Human Motion Biomechanics Lab would help motivate student interest in biomechanics and in research. Fifty percent of the students agreed or strongly agreed that the lab helped them become interested in biomechanics, while only 25% reported that it helped them become interested in research.

Figure 2. Replies to the seven questions from Table 2.

3.2 Open-ended Survey Responses

Eight of the 52 respondents commented that they would prefer having “better defined goals and deliverables” and “more organized deliverable requirements.” Most students are not used to more open-ended projects and have difficulty discerning deliverables from a memo (see Appendix). One of the group data collection sessions did not work properly, so several students from that group commented on this as an area for improvement. Four students provided positive comments in the Additional comments section, indicating that “No drastic improvements, everything worked surprisingly well” and “I enjoyed it.”

3.3 Student submissions

Most of the students were able to develop Matlab programs to analyse the kinematics of the rowers. Many struggled with creating animations of the motion, and commented that this was the most time-consuming aspect of the assignment. Although the majority of students realized that they needed to write their memos to the company, many turned in a typical lab report and did not consider their audience. There was also a great deal of variance in how students addressed moving the height of the seat. Some students performed some research into the biomechanics of the knee and injuries, while others did not put much thought into their interpretations of the knee angles. On the survey, one student mentioned that they thought the rehab company “would offer the specifications of what the flexion angle is and how much they want” and that this part of the lab felt a little contrived.

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

A Rowing MEA was introduced into a dynamics course that uses Matlab for computer simulation of dynamic mechanisms. This provided a realistic context for why students might be required to perform this type of analysis in a workplace environment and exposed them to state-of-the art motion analysis equipment. One of our goals is to incorporate this research laboratory more into our teaching, and as an added benefit

many top students who completed this activity applied to be research assistants in our Human Motion Biomechanics Lab.

The simulation also helped students recognize the time-varying nature of dynamics – all too often we only solve mechanics problems “at an instant in time.” By solving kinematics of the linkage through several cycles and creating an animation, students obtained a better feel for how the angular velocities and accelerations of the knee and shank change as a function of time.

The MEA appeared to increase student motivation, as expressed in the survey. Students seemed to be engaged during the data collection, and appreciated seeing the application of dynamics in the research lab (several posters of different projects are placed throughout the lab). We were able to incorporate all six principles in the MEA (refer to Table 2), although not all students wrote strong memos directly to the client as part of the Model Documentation principle.

Although the lab was successful, several recommendations can be made for future implementations. As in many project-based assignments, students are often uncomfortable when specific lists of deliverables and instructions are not provided. Care must be taken when building the assignment, and often some online quizzes beforehand can be used to ask students to identify the customer, list the deliverables they identify from the memo, and to provide questions about the assignment. Classroom discussions can then be used to help clarify what is expected in the submission.

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Memorandum

To: Biomechanics Engineering Team
From: Emma Williams, Senior R&D Manager at Rogue Fitness
Date: October 15, 2016
RE: Kinematics Data on Concept 2 Model D Rowing Ergometer

Hello Students,

My name is Emma Williams. I am an R&D engineer at Rogue Fitness, and am excited to be collaborating with your company to increase the efficacy of our Concept 2 Model D Rowing Ergometer. We have contracted with the *Cal Poly Human Motion Biomechanics Lab* to examine the motion of an athlete on our most current rowing machine. Over the past week, kinematic data from the athlete have been taken using the Concept 2 Rowing Ergometer. It will be your team's responsibility to analyze these data.

Unfortunately, the hip marker fell off of the athlete during the acquisition of the kinematic data. To avoid the cost and labor of rescheduling time with the athletes and the motion lab, we would like your team to develop a model of the lower body that accurately predicts the motion of the hip during rowing exercise on our device. We are certain that this is possible with your creativity and the kinematic data we were able to capture successfully. With the model your team creates, we ask that you provide a plot showing the velocity of the hip as a function of time. Your team should compare this model velocity to the velocity of the hip marker prior to it falling off. This will confirm the accuracy of the model. Also, with the model your team creates, we ask that you provide a 2D stick figure animation of the experimental data. This will allow our engineers to better visualize and interpret the analysis your team provides.

One of Rogue Fitness's main concerns with the rowing machine is ensuring that athletes are experiencing safe ranges of motion of the knee while using the rower. At Rogue Fitness we would like to be certain that our design is as safe and effective as possible. To do this we must ensure that our rowers are experiencing the proper range of flexion and extension in the knee while rowing, especially if they are recovering from injury.

Accordingly, as a part of your analysis, we ask that your team provide a plot of knee flexion/extension angle as a function of time for the rowing experiment. Finally, we are considering making some design changes to our rowers. We ask that your team analyse the effect that the moving the seat height up or down by 10 cm has on the range of experienced by the athlete on the rowing machine. From this analysis we ask that you compare the range of motion of the knee for various seat heights while using the rowing machine. Please also make any design suggestions that you have for protecting our customers, or for any variations on the design that you think might be innovative and help increase our sales.

I look forward to seeing the great work your team produces,

Emma Williams

Sr.R&D Manager
Rogue Fitness